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The State of Police Legitimacy Through the People's Trust and Satisfaction in the Performance of the Police of Their Duties

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ABSTRACT

People are likely to cooperate with the police when they view their authority as legitimate. Police legitimacy is established by the people's trust in them and the people's satisfaction in the way they perform their duties. This study surveyed and correlated the community people's trust and satisfaction in the police's performance of their duties. There were 2,381 respondents from the different provinces of the Cordillera Administrative Region, Philippines, who participated in the survey. The respondents moderately trust the police and were much satisfied with the way they performed their duties. Age group makes a significant difference in the extent of trust, while gender and age group make a significant difference in the respondents' extent of satisfaction. Pearson's r ($r=.090$) shows there is a weak correlation between the trust of the people to the police and their extent of satisfaction on the way the police performed their duties. It is concluded that trust and satisfaction are independent of each other insofar as police legitimacy is concerned. The police should therefore work on improving their image and demonstrating competence in performing their duties so that the people will cooperate with them and appreciate what they are doing.

INTRODUCTION

Thomas Hobbes' *Leviathan* describes a society of incessant insecurity without a government to give its citizens the safety of law and order, protecting them from each other and from foreign enemies (Hobbes, n.d.). According to the Philippine Constitution of 1987, the people's protection and service are the state's primary responsibility. The police are the branch of the government responsible with ensuring the maintenance of peace and order among the various institutions. The notion of legitimacy is essential to the execution of laws. According to empirical data (Luki, N., Bajovi, V. Tiar, & Eman, 2015), the sense of legitimacy promotes adherence to the law and collaboration with the institutions tasked with enforcing various types of social control. Legitimacy requires that the target population accepts the institution's authority to direct their behavior and compliance with directives (Bradford, Hohl, Jackson, & MacQueen, 2015). When the public sees the police as having legitimate power, they are more likely to comply and assist them (Mazerolle, Bennet, Davis, Sargeant, & Manning, 2013). In a democratic society, the National Institute of Justice (2016) stressed the significance of the public's impressions while reviewing policing. Given that the police are there to serve all residents equally, the public's active involvement in assessing the work of the police is crucial (Jackson & Bradford, 2009). To find out what influences people's perceptions of the police, several research have been. Horowitz (2007) discovered that how an officer acts and behaves has a significant impact on how the public views them. Positive attitudes are influenced by an officer's fair and polite behavior, and interpersonal interactions have the biggest influence on perceptions (Sunshine and Tyler, 2003; Tyler and Hou; 2002).

Public trust increases police efficacy and legitimacy (Lyons, 2002). Trust in law enforcement is essential to the perception of police legitimacy so that the public will feel obligated to obey the law and respect judgments made by lawful authority (Friedman, 2014). According to Sunshine & Tyler (2003) and the International Association of Chiefs of Police (n.d.), trust develops when the public believes that the police pay attention to and address their issues. Therefore, it's critical to prevent further declines in public faith in the police because losing that trust would be detrimental to everyone (Jan, 2016). However, because there are situations that affect the subjective feelings and behaviors of people, trust is prone to either rise or diminish (Koivumäki & Pyriä, 2012).

Most surveys in post-Soviet Russia found that barely 10–20% of people trust the police (Shlapentokh, 2006). According to Gerber and Mendelson (2008), only 3% of Russians felt that the police "truly deserved" their trust, while 23% said they "probably deserved it," 36% said "probably not," and 29% answered "not all" (indicating a general mistrust of Russians toward the police). In 2015, 25% of Americans reported having "great deal," 27% "quite a lot," 30% "some," 16% "very little," and 2% "none" faith in the police (Jones, 2015). In 2016, 36% of Americans reported having "a lot of confidence" in the police, while 41% reported having "some confidence," while only 14% of Black people reported having "a lot of confidence" and 41% reported having "some confidence" (Morin & Stepler, 2016). As well, citizens in Eastern and some Southern European nations report having low level of trusts in the police (Jackson, Hough, Bradford, Pooler, Hohl, & Kuha, 2011), with Romania receiving the lowest ratings (Andreescu, Keeling, Voinic, & Toneas, 2012). These numbers demonstrate the ostensibly low level of

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public trust in the police. The Nordic nations, which were assessed to have the highest levels of trust in their police and feel that the police have power and authority, were some of the nations with high trust ratings (Jackson, *et al.*, 2011). These studies used frequency counts to examine how many respondents trusted or did not trust the police, as well as how satisfied or dissatisfied they were with the police. Additionally, they did not examine the precise areas in which the public trusted the police and the precise responsibilities with which they were happy. These are the areas of the literature that this study will fill in.

The Philippine National Police's divisive national anti-drug campaign has tarnished the police's reputation throughout the country. Therefore, the circumstances at the time the researchers carried out this study were vital to the development of the public's impressions of police officers and their performance in carrying out their tasks. 16 cities and one municipality in the National Capital Region (NCR) were surveyed by the National Police Commission (NAPOLCOM) between November 8 and 14, 2016. According to the findings, public impressions of the lifestyle, morals, and ethics of police officers at the NCRPO have dropped by 11.61 percent, from 44.2% rating in 2014 to 32.6% in 2016. (ABS-CBN News, 2017). Similar circumstances existed five years earlier, according to the findings of the Pulse Asia study, when 26.6% of Filipinos said the Philippine National Police (PNP) was the country's most corrupt institution (ABS-CBN News, 2011). The police force in the nation is indeed rife with problems, and individuals from all walks of life have condemned their work. The PNP recognized this scenario in the middle of the 1990s, which is why they developed a program on community-oriented policing (Philippine National Police, 1995). However, despite the program's institutionalization, trust issues persist, as seen by the aforementioned data.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to empirical research (Luki, N., Bajovi, V. Tiar, & Eman, 2015), people are more likely to obey the law and work with the institutions tasked with implementing various types of social control when they feel that their actions are legitimate. Legitimacy suggests that the population accepts the institution's claim to authority and accepts that they have a responsibility to follow the institution's rules (Bradford, Hohl, Jackson, & MacQueen, 2015). When the public views the police as genuine authorities, they are more likely to comply with their orders and assist them (Mazerolle, Bennet, Davis, Sargeant, & Manning, 2013).

Legitimacy is examined and assessed in several ways. Among the measures were the requirement to obey the law and the police solely (Reisig & Lloyd, 2009), trust and confidence in the judiciary (Murphy & Cherney, 2012), and a commitment to common objectives and values (Tyler & Jackson, 2014). However, some experts contest the accuracy of drawing inferences regarding the

connection between adherence to the law and legitimacy (Eisner & Nivette, 2013). These are traditional methods for examining legitimacy, claim Bottoms and Tankebe (2012). Other factors must be taken into account.

Trust in the police represents their legitimacy as a whole, therefore its professional and policy context cannot be studied in isolation (Schaap, 2020). Trust in the police is a reflection of trust in the institution as a whole, therefore an individual's behavior reflects on the department or organization as a whole. Trust includes a belief that the police are aware of the community's needs, treat citizens with respect, treat them fairly, and allow them a voice in discussing issues that affect the neighborhood beyond how well the officers are performing their duties (Jackson & Bradford, 2009).

Most surveys in post-Soviet Russia found that barely 10–20% of people trust the police (Shlapentokh, 2006). According to Gerber and Mendelson (2008), only 3% of Russians felt that the police "truly deserved" their trust, while 23% said they "probably deserved it," 36% said "probably not," and 29% answered "not all" (indicating a general mistrust of Russians toward the police). In 2015, 25% of Americans reported having "great deal," 27% "quite a lot," 30% "some," 16% "very little," and 2% "none" faith in the police (Jones, 2015). In 2016, 36% of Americans reported having "a lot of confidence" in the police, while 41% reported having "some confidence," while only 14% of Black people reported having "a lot of confidence" and 41% reported having "some confidence" (Morin & Stepler, 2016). As well, citizens in Eastern and some Southern European nations report having little faith in the police (Jackson, Hough, Bradford, Pooler, Hohl, & Kuha, 2011), with Romania receiving the lowest ratings (Andreescu, Keeling, Voinic, & Toneas, 2012). These numbers demonstrate the ostensibly low level of public trust in the police. The Nordic nations, which were assessed to have the highest levels of trust in their police and feel that the police have power and authority, were some of the nations with high trust ratings (Jackson, *et al.*, 2011).

Gender, age, and race have an impact on how satisfied the public is with the police (Dai & Johnson, 2009; Wu *et al.*, 2009), with females more likely than males to have a favorable opinion of the police (Ivkovic, 2008). According to Johnson, age had no effect on the public's contentment with the police in 30% of studies, but in 70% of studies, older individuals were shown to have a more positive attitude toward the police than younger people. Aday & Krabill (2006) provided an explanation for this, stating that the police typically use discretion when reacting to offenses against the elderly.

These examples of literature used surveys to gather their data, and their reporting emphasized frequency and percentage. The factors of trust, satisfaction, safety, and security were measured using weighted mean and standard deviation in the current study. This study focused on the police's capacity to exhibit their personal and professional characteristics based on their Ethical

Doctrine Manual and the manner in which they carry out their duties, as opposed to previous studies that also examined interactions between the police and the public in measuring trust and satisfaction. Prior research did not examine community safety and security issues that might influence residents' trust and satisfaction with the police. This study filled in these holes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this work, a quantitative approach—specifically, a descriptive and correlation approach—was adopted. The Cordillera Administrative Region's five provinces and one city were the locations of this study. There were more female participants than male. 64% (1,526) of the responders were female, and 36% were male (855). This may be partially explained by the finding made during data collection that men were less willing to fill out surveys than women. In comparison to the men, women participated with greater fervor. 1,475 students and 906 non-students participated, based on status. 62% of respondents were students, compared to 38% who were not students. In terms of age group, 43% of participants were between the ages of 15 and 25. (1,022). The 24-35 age group came in second at 14% (320), followed by the

35-44 age group at 13% (297), the 55-64 age group at 11% (263), the 45-54 age group at 10% (250), and the age group 65+ at 9%. (229).

To handle the information gathered from the surveys, we employed both descriptive and inferential statistics. The weighted mean and standard deviation were applied to the descriptive questions. The respondents were given a Likert type scale to act as a reference for ranking the various indicators. The t-test was employed to identify whether there were appreciable gender variations in the respondents' perceptions of the inferential questions. The significant perceptions based on age and social standing in the community were identified using an ANOVA. To ascertain whether there was a relationship between trust and contentment, Pearson Product Moment was utilized. This study was given approval by the Research Ethics Committee of one higher education institution in the Philippines.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Trust of the people towards the police

A larger proportion of respondents have much trust in the police's capacity to work with the government to safeguard the community's residents' security and safety.

Table 1: The extent of trust of the people towards the police (N=2,381)

How much trust do you have in the ability of the police to	Mean	DI	Sd
1. care about the peace and order situation in your community?	2.88	M	1.01
2. be transparent in his/her actions?	2.58	M	1.04
3. demonstrate openness in listening to your concerns?	2.65	M	1.08
4. be honest with all his/her activities?	2.62	M	1.06
5. provide service to everyone without discrimination?	2.64	M	1.07
6. keep the confidential information you mention to him/her?	2.70	M	1.08
7. remain neutral in matters involving his/her relatives?	2.58	M	1.05
8. refrain from engaging in any activity that conflicts with his/her duties as a public servant?	2.67	M	1.08
9. stick to high standards of morality?	2.71	M	1.07
10. respect the rights of others?	2.73	M	1.08
11. demonstrate proper conduct in dealing with people in the community?	2.68	M	1.07
12. exercise legal authority in performing his/her duties?	2.73	M	1.06
13. practice humility in performing his/her duties?	2.62	M	1.06
14. observe accepted procedures in accomplishing his/her task?	2.70	M	1.07
15. respond immediately to the safety needs of your community?	2.71	M	1.06
16. demonstrate professionalism in performing his/her duties?	2.6539	M	1.07
17. put the interest of the public over his/her own?	2.6850	M	1.04
18. efficiently handle situations requiring his/her help?	2.7169	M	1.08
19. ensure that peace and order are maintained in the community?	2.6783	M	1.09
20. cooperate with the government in ensuring the security and safety of the people in the community?	3.1180	M	1.08
Overall	2.7057	M	.116

However, the standard deviation (1.08) contrasts with the item with the highest standard deviation and reveals a modest dispersion of responses (1.09). According to this data, the police were seen favorably by the majority of the respondents because they openly showed their support for and conformity with the government. Although this item had a lower mean of 2.57 compared to the 3.11 of the item on the ability, more respondents agreed that they trust the police to maintain peace and order in the neighborhood. These data back up Goldsmith's

(2005) assertion that the public's faith in the police is directly correlated with how well the police do their duties. It should be remembered that the police are the government's agency responsible for ensuring that there is peace and order in the community; as such, they are required to uphold the rule of law, enforce regulations, and maintain strategic control over the environment (Chermak & Weiss, 2005). In Serbia, the public views the police as "a body that exists to safeguard the system and as a tool of the government rather than the

people,” according to the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe’s assessment from 2004.

The ability of the police to care about the peace and order situation in the community received the highest rating from the majority of respondents among the personal characteristics; however, this indicator also obtained the lowest standard deviation, suggesting that the respondents’ agreement with this indicator was lower than that with the others. The respondents felt that they could trust the police more in other areas, such as their ability to respect others’ rights, uphold high moral standards, and protect confidentiality, even if keeping peace and order is their primary responsibility. Some people have noted that the cops this time around are more disciplined and compliant with their orders.

The majority of respondents said that they had a great deal of trust in the police to carry out their tasks with humility and honesty, to offer non-discriminatory service, to pay attention to the worries of the public, and to be open and honest about their activities. In human relations, communicating with others is essential since it affects how we handle or treat others. The communication process includes the capacity to listen. However, the respondents gave this a low ranking because they noticed that some police don’t want to hear the justifications of people, particularly children and repeat criminals in the neighborhood. This attitude raises the possibility that some police officers are prejudiced and have a propensity for labeling.

Among the professional characteristics, majority of the respondents gave the lowest ratings on the indicators about the demonstration of professionalism in performing duties (2.65) and the adoption of a neutral stance on matters involving family members (2.58). The indicators about demonstrating proper conduct in dealing with people and refraining from activities that show a conflict of interest relate to professionalism were given similar low ratings. Some respondents clamored for the police to exercise patience in dealing with people who were quarreling because they aggravated the situation, and in handling rude and disrespectful people because there were reasons for this behaviors. The professionalism of the older police officers was appreciated by many of the respondents, especially when they responded to calls for assistance when there was a disturbance in the community. The unprofessional conduct of the younger police officers was noticed by some respondents like the police officers were rude in their language and behavior. There were also observations that some police officers were very friendly to some people in the community, making them familiar with each other. This affected the

objectivity of the police officer in exercising his legal duties, accordingly.

The respondents’ trust in the police is higher when they are acting in a professional manner (2.73 vs. 2.68), which is a sign that they want the police to work on developing some of their personal qualities like openness, honesty, transparency, listening with an open mind, objectivity, morality, and the capacity to respect the rights of others. More particularly, the issue of the police’s objectivity in handling cases involving their relatives needs to be addressed because subjectivity interferes with their efficiency and effectiveness in carrying out their community service obligations. A larger degree of trust would be attained if they showed a noticeable improvement in their personality. The exhibition of their professional attributes is equally crucial because it demonstrates the level of expertise and abilities they possess.

The majority of respondents place a lot of trust in the police’s capacity to carry out their tasks. In this regard, a research conducted by Vuković (2009) in a few Serbian municipalities found that residents believe the police should focus more on reducing crime, upholding the peace and keeping public order, as well as safeguarding persons and property. However, nearly 50% of respondents believe that all residents are treated fairly by the police. Similar to this, residents of the Russian Federation and Bulgaria have the least favorable views of how the police treat their fellow citizens (Meško , Hacin, & Eman, 2014), and individuals in Eastern and occasionally Southern European nations report having less trust in the government (Jackson, Hough, Bradford, Pooler, Hohl, & Kuha, 2011). On the other hand, several studies indicate that people have a high level of trust in the police, particularly in Spain and Nordic nations (Meško, *et al.* 2014) and Jackson, *et al.* (2011).

According to Age Group

The 45-54 age group provided the indicators with the greatest mean (2.9169), while the 65+ age group provided the lowest mean (2.5193). According to the ANOVA results, there is a significant difference between the respondents’ responses by age group at the 5% level of significance. The findings show that the respondents’ levels of trust in the police varied significantly by age group, particularly for those in the 45–54 and 65+ age groups. The findings support Bridenball & Jesilow’s (2008) observation that younger people are more prone to have a hostile attitude toward the police. The majority of Philadelphia’s youth reportedly reported having a bad attitude about the police, according to Carr, Napolitano, and Keating’s 2007 report

Table 2: ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between Groups	1.819	5	.364	16.516	.000
Within Groups	2.512	114	.022		
Total	4.331	119			

significant at 5% (p<.05)

According to Status

The t-test results show no significant differences in the trust level of both groups according to status, that is, regardless of status, the respondents trusted much the police.

Satisfaction of the Community People on The Performance of the Police

More than half of the respondents' remarks were observations about how the police conducted their

Table 3: Independent samples test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Trust	Equal variances assumed	.087	.770	-1.482	38	.147	-.05506	.03715	-.13026	.02014
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.482	37.090	.147	-.05506	.03715	-.13032	.02020

*not significant at 5% ($p > .05$)

patrols. Since the majority of crimes occur at night, they saw that the police were not always visible, especially throughout the night. As a result, multiple requests were made to increase patrols during this time. It was also reported that very few police were doing foot patrols.

Accordingly, the police frequently drive vehicles that cannot travel into alleyways or down hills to where the residences were located. The respondents preferred that the police do foot patrols in order for them to conduct house to house visits and engage with residents, as this is

Table 4: The extent of satisfaction of the community people on the performance of the police (N=2,381)

How satisfied are you with the competence of the police in	Mean	Std. Deviation
1 communicating with the people in your community?	2.61	1.00
2 assisting the community in maintaining peace and order?	2.63	1.06
3 directing the flow of vehicular traffic?	2.60	1.01
4 arresting the criminals in the community?	2.63	1.04
5 solving crimes in the community?	2.58	1.03
6 assisting during disasters?	2.63	1.06
7 making themselves visible during community activities that require their presence?	2.61	1.03
8 responding when you call them for assistance?	2.62	1.03
9 handling victims of crimes?	2.61	1.05
10 maintaining discipline among people during public gatherings?	2.63	1.04
11 calming conflicts in the community?	2.60	1.04
12 investigating reported crimes?	2.64	1.03
13 patrolling their assigned stations?	2.64	1.03
14 responding to road accidents?	2.68	1.04
15 enforcing the ordinances/laws?	2.67	1.03
Overall	2.63	.02

a crucial component of satisfaction (National Institute of Justice, n.d.). Street visibility was one of the four factors that Larsen and Blair (2009) included in their analysis of how satisfied people are with the police.

The respondents were also quite satisfied with the police's ability to respond to persons and situations. Out of the analyzed functions, this one had the highest mean. Despite their high levels of satisfaction, some respondents claimed that it takes too long for the police to arrive when they are called, particularly when there are disturbances in the neighborhood, pubs, and other places of business. This shows that the respondents were unhappy with the police's response time. Others spoke about the mistakes made by the police when they interact with someone seeking help, such as their failure to grasp the person's language and their impoliteness while posing questions. Among the stated

functions, the ability of the police to enforce the laws had the highest mean, indicating that the respondents were satisfied with the way the police carried out this duty. The respondents noted certain areas for improvement, such as regularly and fairly enforcing the ordinances, even if they were generally satisfied with the competence displayed by the police in carrying out this role. Many people have noted that police officers occasionally disregard community infractions such as improper parking, excessive speeding, driving without a license, selling alcohol to minors, letting minors into pubs, and vandalizing property. It was observed that police personnel occasionally resisted becoming involved in disputes, especially when they knew the parties involved. Evidently, the respondents have observed some subjectivity and inconsistent enforcement of laws by the police. As a result, the respondents' personal experience

with the police influences whether or not they are satisfied with them (National Institute of Justice, n.d.) Four key factors have been identified by Larsen and Blair (2009) as influencing how satisfied citizens are with the work of the police. These factors include police initiatives to prevent crime, street visibility, officer reaction times to crimes in progress, and police-community interactions. No matter if the person initiating the contact or the police,

Skogan (2005) discovered that police engagement affects satisfaction. Additionally, he discovered that courteous, prompt, fair, and helpful police behavior increases residents' happiness (Hawdon, 2003).

According to gender

The findings support Cao, Frank, and Cullen's (1996) observation that females are more likely than males to

Table 5: Independent samples test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means					
		F	Sig.	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference Lower
Trust	Equal variances assumed	.002	.969	-4.485	28	.000	-.04579	.01021	-.06670
	Equal variances not assumed			-4.485	27.996	.000	-.04579	.01021	-.06670

*significant at 5% ($p < .05$)

have a favorable attitude toward the police. The results show a substantial difference between males and females' satisfaction with the competence of the police in carrying out their duties. Differences in experiences and frequency of encounter with the police may be to blame for the disparity. The findings imply that in order to satisfy ladies, police officers must raise their level of competence in terms of efficiency, speed, and effectiveness in carrying out their duties.

According to Age Group

At the 5% level of significance, the ANOVA findings showed substantial variations between the respondents' responses when taking into account their age group. This finding suggests that age is a factor in people's satisfaction with the police's competence. The Tukey HSD showed the following areas of significance at the 0.05 level: the satisfaction of the 15–24 and 25–34 age groups significantly differed from that of the 45–54 and

Table 6: ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between Groups	.540	5	.108	31.731	.000
Within Groups	.286	84	.003		
Total	.827	89			

significant at 5% ($p < .05$)

65+ age groups; that of the 35–44 age group significantly differed from that of the 55–64 and 65+ age groups; that of the 44–55 age group significantly differed from that of the 15–24, 25–34, 55–64, and 65+ age groups; and that of the 55–64 and 65+ age groups; the 44–55 age group's satisfaction was significantly different from that of the 15-24, 25-34, 55-64, and 65+ age groups; the 55-64 age group's satisfaction was significantly different from that

of the 34-44, 45-54, and 65+ age groups; and the 65+ age group's satisfaction was significantly different from that of all the other age groups. The National Institute of Justice (n.d.) reported that age differences in satisfaction with the police was evident, with respondents aged 18-22 having a significantly lower level of satisfaction.

According to Status

Table 7: Independent samples test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means					
		F	Sig.	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference Lower
Trust	Equal variances assumed	.002	.969	-4.485	28	.000	-.04579	.01021	-.06670

Equal variances not assumed			-4.485	27.996	.000	-.04579	.01021	-.06670
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*significant at 5% ($p < .05$)

At .05 level of confidence, there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of the students and non-students regarding the competence of the police in performing their tasks.

According to Age Group

At the 5% level of significance, the ANOVA findings showed substantial variations between the respondents' responses when taking into account their age group. This finding suggests that age is a factor in people's satisfaction with the police's competence. The Tukey

HSD showed the following areas of significance at the 0.05 level: the satisfaction of the 15–24 and 25–34 age groups significantly differed from that of the 45–54 and 65+ age groups; that of the 35–44 age group significantly differed from that of the 55–64 and 65+ age groups; that of the 44–55 age group significantly differed from that of the 15–24, 25–34, 55–64, and 65+ age groups; and that of the 55–64 was considerably different from that of the 34-44, 45-54, and 65+ age groups; and the satisfaction of the 65+ age group was significantly different from those of all the other age groups.

Table 8: ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between Groups	.540	5	.108	31.731	.000
Within Groups	.286	84	.003		
Total	.827	89			

significant at 5% ($p < .05$)

The relationship of trust in the police and satisfaction in the performance of their duties

The level of community satisfaction with police performance and community trust in law enforcement have a weak link ($r = .090$). The weak association is also not even statistically significant at 5% ($p > .05$). Accordingly, the correlation is assigned to chance because it is implied that the sample's level of correlation is not shared by the population. The variable in community trust in the police only explains 0.81% ($r^2 = .0081$) of the overall variance in the level of satisfaction. In other words, confidence in the police is not a factor in the context of this study when determining satisfaction with their performance, just as pleasure with the performance of the police is not a

factor in determining trust in them. As a result, trust and satisfaction are separate ideas. According to Cao (2015), satisfaction is motivated by experiences and internally focused. If satisfaction is a condition of the mind, trust is not (Dai & Johnson, 2009; Zhao, Tsai, Ren & Lai, 2014). The declaration of satisfaction with police is motivated by experiences and internally focused. If satisfaction is a condition of the mind, trust is not (Dai & Johnson, 2009; Zhao, Tsai, Ren & Lai, 2014). The declaration of satisfaction with police services results from a perceived satisfaction of a service from the other party. Trust "involves a result associated with some form of risk to one's ultimate welfare," according to Cao (2015).

Table 9: Correlation between trust and satisfaction

		Trust	Satisfaction
Trust	Pearson Correlation	1	.090
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.750
	N	20	15
Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.090	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.750	
	N	15	15

Figure 1: The Scatter Plot of Trust on Police and the Extent of Satisfaction of the Community to the Performance of the Police in their Duties

CONCLUSION

The police forces in the provinces under consideration have not successfully gained the trust of the locals. The police must uphold their sworn obligations to win the public's trust and perform well to ensure that the public is satisfied with their services because, as this study's findings show, trust in the police and satisfaction with their performance are independent variables that are not related to one another. There are still gaps in the police officers' skills and competency, despite the fact that they have earned the community's trust via the way they carry out their responsibilities and interact with the public. People's sense of security may increase if they have a

strong sense of the legitimacy of the police.

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